

A review of synthetic and molecular model study towards fixing up bio-active chiral centre at C₂₈ of Lasonolide-A, an anticancer macrolide : A new chiral pool approach

Paramita Kar*, B. V. Rao, J. A. R. P. Sarma, B. Chowdhury, K. Nagaiah and M. K. Gurjar

Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad-500 007, India

E-mail : paramita_k@yahoo.com; paramitakar2001@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 22 September 2004, accepted 3 March 2005

A new chiral pool approach has been demonstrated here to fix-up directly a chiral centre at C₂₈ by sharpless asymmetric epoxidation to a model system of Lasonolide A – the potent cytotoxic anticancer macrolide.

In continuation of our work as reported earlier¹, here in this paper we have described another approach to chiral pool synthesis. The chiral pool approach extends to the formation of stereoselective synthesis of chiral side chain of model of Lasonolide-A (corresponding cyclohexyl system) using Sharpless Asymmetric Epoxidation (SAE) reaction. The intramolecular Claisen rearrangement is considered to be the key step of the synthesis of the side chain.

Lasonolide-A

Retrosynthesis :

The retrosynthesis of model of Lasonolide-A is designed according to SAE chiral pool and intramolecular Claisen rearrangement protocol where the chirality retains as usual. According to the novel strategy envisages, which involves stereoselective synthesis of *S*-(4)-cyclohexyl-3-hydroxybut-1-ene followed by formation of corresponding benzyl derivative as follows.

2-Cyclohexyl-1-ethanol (**1**) was oxidized to corresponding aldehyde (**2**). In the ¹H NMR spectrum, the aldehyde proton appeared as ¹H singlet at δ 9.75. *trans* Wittig reac-

tion of 2-cyclohexylacetaldehyde using two carbon ylide yielded ethyl-4-cyclohexyl(*E*)-2-butenolate (**3**). In the

*Present address : 4/4-C, Jadu Mitra Lane, Ground Floor, Kolkata-700 004, India.

^1H NMR spectrum, one of the ene proton (H_3) appeared as δ 5.75 as doublet with J 14.28 Hz which resembled *trans* coupling (which is a proof of the formation of *trans* double bond) whereas the other ene proton (H_2) appeared at δ 6.80–7.00 as one proton multiplet.

3 was then treated with DIBAL-H at -78°C in presence of DCM to yield 4-cyclohexyl(*E*)-2-buten-1-ol (**4**; Scheme 1). The allylic protons of **4** appeared as multiplet as δ 5.70–

Scheme 1

5.40, temperature (-23°C). Thus sharpless asymmetric epoxidation of the allylic alcohol yielded corresponding asymmetric epoxide 3-cyclohexyl-methyl-(2*R*, 3*R*)-oxiran-2-yl methanol (**5**). The stereochemical assignment were based on hypothesis reported by Gao *et al.*². The chiral epoxide (**5**) was eluted by ethyl acetate : pet. ether (20 : 80) solvent mixture and obtained as 69% of yield. In the ^1H NMR spectrum, the epoxide proton (H_2) appeared at δ 2.90–3.05 as multiplet. In the IR spectrum (neat), the OH-str. frequency appeared at 3400 cm^{-1} . The C–H in epoxide appeared at 2861 cm^{-1} whereas C–O–C in epoxide vibrated at 1030 cm^{-1} . Compound was analysed for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$. M^+ 170 $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -31.103$ (c 1.20, CHCl_3).

Further regioselective opening of this epoxide by Cp_2TiCl_2 gave rise to *R*-(4)-cyclohexyl-3-hydroxy-but-1-ene (**7**) $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = +3.373$, (c 0.73, CHCl_3).

Scheme 2

Here this protocol demonstrated a convenient single step synthesis of optically active secondary alcohol **7**. The high

regioselectivity observed may be due to the participation of the hydroxy group in the T.S. The proposed mechanism is depicted on Scheme 2a.

Scheme 2a

The chiral alcohol was eluted by ethyl acetate : pet. ether (5 : 95) solvent mixture and obtained as 45% yield. The IR spectrum (neat) appeared at 2920 cm^{-1} (C–H str. vibration, olefinic) and 3446 cm^{-1} (OH). In the ^1H NMR spectrum of **7**, the ene protons (H_3 and H_4) were appeared as multiplet at δ 5.00–5.25 and 5.75–5.95. Compound was analysed for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ as (M^+) = 154, δ 5.00–5.25 and 5.75–5.95. Compound was analysed for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ as (M^+) = 154.

Our next target is esterification of the substituted allylic alcohol **7** by 2-benzyloxy-ethanoic acid³ (Scheme 3). The esterification was carried out in presence of 1 equivalent of DCC and 0.3965 eq. of DMAP at 0°C to room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h till white ppt. appeared. The white ppt. was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuum and purified by column chromatography (ethyl acetate : pet. ether : 4 : 96) to obtain 1-cyclohexyl methyl-(1*R*)-3-propenyl-2'-benzyloxy acetate (**8**) as a total yield of 55%.

$[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = -6.46$ (c 1.03, CHCl_3). The IR spectrum (neat) vibrated at 2928 cm^{-1} (C–H str. vib. olefinic), 1760 cm^{-1} (C=O str. vib.), 1120 cm^{-1} [ester C–(CO)–O bond of sat. ester] and 1030 cm^{-1} (ester-O–C–C-vib.). Considering proton NMR values, the vinylic protons appear as multiplet at

Scheme 3

Table 1

Temp. = 300 K

Entry	Formula	Elemental entropy (cal/mol) (Se)	Calculated entropy (cal/mol) (Sc)	ΔS_f = Entropy of formation = (Se-Sc) in (cal/mol)	Heat of formation = ΔH_f in (kcal/mol)	ΔG_f = Gibb's free energy of formation of reaction = $\Delta H_f - T \Delta S_f$ (kcal/mol)	$\delta (\Delta G_f) = G_{p1,2} - \Delta G_{r1,2}$ (kcal/mol)	$\delta (\Delta S_f) = \Delta S_{f1,2} - \Delta S_{fr1,2}$ (cal/mol)
8	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₃	505.1	168.4	-336.7	-103	-2		
8a	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₃	505.1	161.8	-343.3	-120.6	-17.6	-15.6	-6.6
9	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	497	170.9	-326.1	-127.8	-30		
9a	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	497	171.8	-325.2	-144.7	-47.1	-17.1	+0.9

NB : In case of molecular model study the energy value is same for both chiral and racemic systems.

δ 5.74–5.62 and 5.30–5.10. Compound was analysed for C₁₉H₂₈O₃ as M⁺ 302.

The corresponding ester **8** is an important starting material for intramolecular Claisen rearrangement. The methylene CH₂ adjacent to the OBn moiety can generate an anion which migrate via a 3,3 sigma-tropic rearrangement mode to form the required acid. In the Fujisawa method, the chirality has been retained with almost 98% stereoselectivity⁴ and THF is considered to be the best solvent. The ester enolate Claisen rearrangement was tried in three best possible ways (Scheme 4).

As there was no steric hindrance or electronic factor for the failure of this rearrangement, the molecular model study was carried out to resemble the experimental results with the theoretical energy values. We have calculated the thermodynamic factors statistically by MOPAC (version 6.0) with AM 1 methods (in Table 1) for the model and the actual tetrahydropyranyl systems.

Reaction 1 :

Reaction 2 :

For the reaction (**8-8a**), there is enormous decrease in entropy value (-6.6 cal/mol), so the reaction is not spontaneous. But for reaction 2 (**9-9a**), there is slight increase in entropy value (~1.0 cal/mol), and the reaction will occur spontaneously. As the Claisen rearrangement is kinetically controlled, so entropy is the determining factor, not the Gibb's free energy.

The above study is indeed a confirmation of the molecular model study, which clearly showed that the Claisen rearrangement did not work for cyclohexyl system but worked well with pyran system. Anyway our actual system is pyran, derived from sugar moiety. The above protocol is certainly useful to get the chiral unit of **9a**, since the pyran unit is going to be a carbohydrate derivative and the newly generated allylic hydroxy centre at C₂₈ in **1**, can be obtained by sharpless epoxidation followed by reductive opening of the epoxide.

The Claisen rearrangement according to Fujisawa re-

tains the chirality in the rearranged product. Therefore the above protocol is useful to get the required unit (C₂₈-C₃₅) in the optically pure form. The synthesis of the top and bottom half (C₇-C₁₆ and C₁₈-C₂₃) fragments had already been achieved by our group and work is currently under progress towards the total synthesis.

Acknowledgement

One of us (P.K.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi of financial support.

References

1. Paramita Kar, B. V. Rao, K. Nagaiah and M. K. Gurjar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 52.
2. Y. Gao, R. M. Hansor, J. M. Klunder, S. Y. Ko, H. Massamune and K. B. Sharpless, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 5765.
3. A. Hassner and V. Alexanian, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, **46**, 4475; C. Gilon and Y. Klausner, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, **40**, 3811.
4. T. Sato, K. Tajima and T. Fujisawa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **1**, 729.
5. M. J. S. Dewan, E. G. Zoebisch, E. F. Healy and J. J. P. Stewart, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 3902.